

Qualitative Study on Education for National Security and Sustainable Development in Nigeria: Challenges and Way Forward

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Abstract

The critical security crises confronting Nigeria are identified by different names, such as: kidnapping; Boko Haram insurgency; socio-economic agitations; boundary disputes; cultism; corruption; robbery, including pen robbery; looting of the national treasury; election crises; herdsmen brutality; and ethnic rivalry and religious pluralism. Failures in education pose distinct threats to national security. How can education promote security? Many conflicts arise from ignorance and manipulation of ethnic and religious identity. Education, not mere schooling, produces tolerant and civil citizens who are able to understand and live with people from different economic, religious, ethnic, cultural, and other backgrounds. Although it is widely acknowledged that education aids society in the development of new attitudes, values, knowledge, skill, and technique, little is said about how these values are actually developed and changed within individuals, how values may be communicated, and how educational processes within formal and non-formal curriculum may promote such value development. On this note, the paper focuses on the role of education in curbing environmental challenges for national security and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Education, National Security, Challenges, Sustainable Development, Nigeria.

Introduction

In Nigerian society, the word "national security" sprang to prominence during the upheavals that followed the political scuffle of 1966, which signaled the start of the Nigerian civil war, which lasted from 1967 to 1970. The restoration to civil democracy in 1999, following the military's departure from active politics and national administration, saw the word ascend and become common language in our polity. There is no denying that Nigeria is currently dealing with major security issues, which have placed every citizen on edge, especially those in positions of authority and even the security personnel tasked with protecting people and property. Compatriots find it difficult to fall asleep with closed eyes. Since the past four years, Nigeria's insecurity wave, dynamics, and complexity have seen a drastic change. In the hierarchy of Nigeria's societal issues, insecurity used to be one of the least concerning issues, but it has since grown to alarming proportions. At a time when we believed that corruption and power outages were the root of all of our issues, the country's current top concern is insecurity (FinIntell, 2013).

Nigerians now live with a constant sense of fear, dread, and jitteriness. As a result, the government consistently allots a sizable sum of money to security with the intent of resolving these security issues. A quick peek at the daily newspapers in Nigeria will persuade one of the states that the nation is insecure. Youth unrest, kidnapping, bombing, arson, militancy, and insurgency, among other things, have grown prevalent (Ogheneakoke, 2014). This social issue has hindered economic development, human capital development, and national growth. No country can flourish in an unstable environment, according to Robert McNamara, a former president of the World Bank. According to him, stability and peace are essential elements of growth. According to Mordi (2013), the ongoing mayhem and devastation of lives and property in various regions of the country brought on by the threat of BokoHaram in the Northern states, militants, and kidnappers in the South, among others, have stunted Nigeria's growth and stability. As farming and agricultural activities have been hindered, food production has been severely harmed and is on the decline, while oil exploration, exploitation, and export have all suffered in the North and South, respectively.

Concept of National Security in Nigeria

Before defining national security, we must define security. Wikipedia defines security as freedom from or resistance against potential damage (or other unwanted forced change) from others. (<https://en.m.wikipedia.org>), Nmom (2013) defined security as a complete condition of peace for an individual, organization, state, or nation at a specific moment and place. He believed that a relative peace could guarantee excellent life and social cohesion for the survival of a group or nation. From the preceding definitions, security is seen as protecting the general population and is a government-people responsibility. Thus, community policing is a common security term in Nigeria. It protects a state or organization from terrorism, theft, and espionage, as well as anxiety and fear (Ogheneakoke, 2014). Thus, a nation's security interests encompass life and property protection, economic, physiological, and mental well-being, and the ability to pursue goals without interference (Otoibhi, 2012).

Brown (2013) defines national security as the ability to protect the nation's physical integrity and territory, maintain reasonable economic connections with the rest of the world, protect its nature, institutions, and government from outside upheaval, and control its borders. Our most cherished values and beliefs, our democratic way of life, our institutions of governance, and our unity, welfare, and well-being as a nation and people are permanently maintained and continuously reinforced by national security. Quality education, economic power, military strength, diplomacy, and power projection are needed to preserve the nation. It is the nation's individuals, political entities, human associations, and ethnic groups' security interests (Osakwe, 2013). National security is the government's responsibility to protect a nation's citizens, economy, and institutions.

Thus, national security strategy includes the use of diplomatic, economic, and military force in peace and conflict to protect the nation-state. In other words, it means freedom from foreign dominance, which is essential for state survival through economic, diplomatic, power projection, and political power.

National Security and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Modern national security entails developing a nexus of collaborative military, paramilitary, and civic organizations and acquiring and sharing national and cross-border intelligence to improve national and citizen safety and health. Most crucially, modern national security is based on a nation's economic well-being, while the military individual complex helps maintain peace and tranquility in any society. Thus, economic factors largely determine citizen peace and stability. Thus, a nation's economy is its main security pillar. A nation's security is improved when its labor force, especially its youth, is gainfully employed and welfare programmes are created to protect the unemployed and disabled. Education is essential because of this. Education creates productive workers. Modern thought and practice have rejected the idea that national security is restricted to acquiring and storing massive military gear, demonstrating intimidating military power, or traditional military operations, while they may be part of a nation's security architecture. However, today's security depends on development.

Sustainable development in this context means a nation's ability to use its people and capital resources to allow its citizens to dream and achieve their goals in a supportive and well-structured environment. When this is done regularly and sustainably, disturbance and violence decrease and security improves. Late World Bank president Robert McNamara advocated this holistic national security approach. "The world can never be in peace unless people enjoy security in their everyday existence," declared the UNDP (2014) Human Development Report in Usman (2015). The state is responsible for security and sustainable development. Human security empowers residents to discuss unusual security issues and grow the country. Seji et al. (2020) correctly stated that "security is not military hardware, though it may incorporate it, security is not military force, though it may involve it, security is not traditional military activities, though it may encompass it." Security requires progress. Sustainable development means economic, social, and political advancement. It signifies living comfortably.

Concept of Education

For the growth of any society, education is crucial. In fact, every human community that yearns for progress in all senses of the word should not disregard education, according to Freire (1970), who claims that it is a major weapon of social transformation. The Nigerian government understands the value of education for the general development of the country and views it as "an instrument for achieving national development," as evidenced by the following set of educational principles:

1. Education is an instrument for national development and social change
2. Education is vital for the promotion of a progressive and united Nigeria
3. Education maximizes the creative potentials and skills of the individual for self-fulfilment and general development of the society.
4. Education is compulsory and a right of every Nigerian irrespective of gender, social status, religion, colour, ethnic background and any peculiar individual challenges: and

5. Education is to be qualitative, comprehensive, functional and relevant to the needs of the society (FGN, 2014).

To define education, scholars have included "quality." They believed education must be high-quality to fulfill its goals. According to Maduewesi in Seji et al. (2020), excellent education requires that all levels and parts of the educational system, including vocational, practical, and theoretical education, create results that benefit the nation. It involves well-articulated national goals, well-planned curriculum, assessment technique and instruments, data analysis, how to use assessment results, and student quality. He sees poor parenting and a conviction among many adolescents and adults that education and hard effort are not important as the biggest obstacles to decent education.

UNESCO (2015), another UN body, wrote that quality education should promote quality, encourage creative and emotional development, support peace, citizenship, and security, and seek out past global and local cultural values to pass on to future generations. Quality education promotes and improves basic education, reorients educational policies and programs at all levels to address national security and sustainable development, develops public awareness, and provides training and retraining, including higher education, Seji, Philip, and John (2020). Thus, education must be holistic, including qualitative and quantitative processes like "relevant curriculum, availability of adequate human and non-human resources, assessment of educational programmes and processes through proper supervision and evaluation of educational outcomes to ensure quality assurance, control and nation security" (Osakwe, 2013).

Effects of Insecurity in Nigeria

Companies are closing operations in Boko-Haram-ravaged north and oil-rich south-south and moving to neighboring African countries due to loss of life and property. Few companies survive. Construction workers and expatriates working on specialized projects in these places have fled for safety. This has increased the number of homeless youth and made violence easier. This situation worsens poverty and unemployment. They think education underpins social economic progress (Freire, 1970). Islamic extremists have repeatedly kidnapped kids and school facilities in northern states (Chibok Girls and Burnin Yadin Boys Government Schools). Many schools have discontinued academic programs. This has greatly reduced the number of students applying to all academic levels. The University of Maiduguri, one of Nigeria's most cheap universities, now solicits admission through media outreach.

A recent survey found that many students would refuse to serve in the mandatory one-year national youth service corps (NYSC) if assigned to the north. After three weeks of obligatory camping, those accidentally sent north were redeployed. This defeats the 1973 NYSC Act's main purpose (FinIntell, 2013). Nigeria loses worldwide esteem as the security situation worsens. It strains bilateral relations. If this unsightly trend is not addressed immediately, it will negatively impact all development indices and the millennium development target, making vision 2020 a mirage. (2013).

Place of Education in for National Security and Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Education passes on culture. It alters human behavior for good. Education is one of the oldest industries in human history, therefore a society's future depends on the quality of its members' education. Education can avoid, eliminate, or modify violence in Nigeria due to its effects on socioeconomic, moral, and political life. Danmole (2015) claims that only education can create literate and educated citizens. Education improves life, worldview, and adaptability. Education will illumine minds and enthrone right religious knowledge to end deadly religious conflict. It is true that intolerance and fanaticism cause religious bloodshed in Nigeria, but education reduces bad ideals and promotes patriotism, a national value. Fagbemi (2012) proposes that public education can increase Nigerian tolerance and patriotism.

In the NPE (2014), the Federal Government states that "education shall continue to be highlighted in the National Development because education is the most important instrument of change, any fundamental change in the intellectual and social outlook of any society has to be preceded by an educational revolution". Our existing education system prioritizes science and technology over citizenship education, yet it fails to meet its goals. History relocated to senior secondary school. Few students volunteer. Due to social studies' limitations, few young people know Nigeria's history. To promote education access, the Federal Government is supporting private education involvement. However, religious schools and universities may harm national unity. This may not solve morality. Since the institutions create Muslims, Anglicans, Baptists, and Catholics instead of Nigerians, loyalty is now likely to the church or religion rather than the state.

Thus, citizenship education must be strengthened in theory and practice with other topics. Nigerian pride would solve all problems. Nigerian education promotes a fair and equal society (NPE, 2014). This philosophy helps bring peace. Peace and growth result from justly resolving conflicts without tribalism, nepotism, or religious

bias. Educational growth may reduce poverty, maintain national security, and boost regional prosperity, according to Ololube and Egbezor (2022). Education promotes national unity, human capital development, cultural diversity, human rights, and global knowledge chains by increasing access, capacity building, and information exchange. Education builds universal values-based norms, especially in multi-cultural and multi-religious civilizations. Education shares knowledge about culture, science, technology, values, and norms.

Challenges of Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Some of the challenges of education that if eradicated will enhance sustainable development in Nigeria and Africa at large include;

1. Existing Policy framework cannot adequately support education in a global economy due to the following among others:
 - a. Inadequate fidelity in policy implementation, i.e. some relevant parts of the education system do not support policies.
 - b. Policies are not given enough time to produce results due to policy summer sault.
2. Education is not adequately funded due to scarce resources and inadequate public/private partnership in funding education. As a result,
 - a. Teachers' conditions of service is not good and not motivating enough to make them undertake the heavier task of preparing students for an entirely new world.
 - b. Educational infrastructures such as access roads, classrooms, laboratories, etc are in poor condition. Thus, the current learning environment cannot meet the demands of the 21st century learning; etc.
3. Teachers are inadequately trained. Educator preparing programmes in Nigeria are not yet preparing their graduates to possess, teach and assess 21st century knowledge and skills. As a result, they cannot become change agents for embedding 21st century knowledge, skills in core subjects.
4. For pedagogy, for students of social change, the usefulness and essence of training and education cannot be overemphasized. One of the major challenges of education as a tool for development in Africa and Nigeria in particular is that apart from issues of funding and brain-drain, there is a disconnect between realities on the ground and what the children and folk are taught in schools.

The result is that a graduate of Electrical Engineering from a tertiary institution goes out to pay an electrician to do his electrical jobs at home. In social sciences, for instance, students are often taught about the writings of David Easton, Talcot Parson, Adams Smith etc, while we systematically forget about even equally important philosophy for pre-colonial African minds. As such political scientists are taught more about Ancient Greece than pre-colonial Onitsha, Oyo or Calabar.

Education as the way forward

On November 21, 2013, former British Prime Minister Tony Blair addressed the UN counter-terrorism organization that broad-based cross-cultural education is essential to fighting religion-based terrorism. "There is little doubt now regarding the nature of this scourge," he said. That it is extremism founded on religious perversion, a fanaticism that justifies violence against innocent civilians". The Tony Blair Faith Foundation helps reduce religious intolerance, conflict, and extremism under his leadership. He underlined that teaching about diversity, tolerance, and respect is as important as teaching the humanities, sciences, and languages.

"That is why in the 21st century, education is a security issue and not any education but education specifically that opens young minds to the others; who are culturally and religiously different, and shows them how the only future that works is one in which people are respected as equals whatever their faith or culture," Mr. Blair concluded. me in you. We should seek peace. When he observed, Ban Ki-Chef Moon's de Cabinet Susana Malcorra stressed the importance of education in combating radical beliefs that incite hatred and violence and fostering empathy. Markets, schools, places of worship, neighborhoods, and communities have been destroyed by mindless bloodshed. That we must collaborate to combat this dreadful epidemic and engage young people to show them a world of fairness, justice, opportunity, and empowerment.

One of the most significant international organizations, Global Partnership for Education channels billions of dollars from over twenty countries to strengthen education systems in fifty-nine developing countries. Former Australian Prime Minister Julia Gillard, now Chairwoman of Global Partnership for Education (GPE), promotes education investment as enlightened self-interest. That anyone concerned about promoting economic growth and combating extremism should create classrooms and train teachers. That tens of millions of youngsters in sub-Saharan Africa lack primary education. UNESCO reports hundreds of millions more who leave school illiterate due to substandard education. "In some ways the argument for getting every child into school speaks for itself, but in our busy noisy world, even things that should be obvious have to be spoken for and championed,"

Gillard said of Nigerian schoolgirls. She said the Boko Haram kidnapping of Nigerian schoolgirls should be a warning about extremism and a call to preserve education. Education in such communities is powerful and important. "That they obviously believe education is strong, so powerful that they wish to deny those girls". The global education crisis has been highlighted by the Nigerian scenario. Gillard hoped it would galvanize the world to come to the rescue of the school girls in Nigeria and to ensure that the power of education is given to children even in the most difficult circumstances.

Conclusion

For education to lead to economic growth and national security for sustainable development, there must be equitable access through adequate public investment in classrooms, relevant curriculum, trained teachers, technology for learning and teaching, teaching and learning materials, and enough time for all levels of learning. Efficient education management aside, the economy should be well managed to translate the nation's wealth to people's welfare through adequate investment in health services, education services, security, enabling environment, and employment opportunities to maximize skilled labor's contribution to national productivity and society's growth. In a knowledge society, proper research funding encourages the acquisition, accumulation, adoption, adaptation, and application of local and international innovation and knowledge. Education, innovation, and technical systems should work together to turn classroom lessons into sustainable economic production.

As citizens worked, insecurity would decrease. Finally, controlling education for national security and sustainable development in Nigeria and Africa should not be limited to schooling for job and life. Instead, it should be conceptualized as a system-wide formal, non-formal, and informal education and training well designed and coordinated to empower the citizens and future of Nigeria and Africa in the areas of productive and environmental skills, spirit (consciousness), science, and technologies needed to stimulate, strengthen, spread, and sustain structural transformation and vigorously reduce security problems in Nigeria and Africa.

National security is a Nigerian thinking problem (psyche). Nigeria has the human and material resources for prosperity, safety, and security. This requires changing Nigerians' thinking. Education must change their minds. Proper education must begin at birth and continue until death. Such education must utilize all necessary tools to reorient their brains into a proper value system; into proper concepts and the context of "wealth and success", "safety and welfare", "freedom and liberty", "justice and fair play", "rule of law", and "responsibility". These are mind-made. Only "education" can bend or unbend the mind.

Recommendations

This paper recommends the under listed points/suggestions, as panacea for this seemingly intractable insecurity challenges in Nigeria:

1. The Federal Government (FG) should establish and implement policies and programs to address the root causes of insecurity in Nigeria, such as high illiteracy, poverty, unemployment, environmental degradation, lack of infrastructure amenities, unequal development, and others.
2. The government should phase out the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) and replace it with a more effective agency or declare an educational emergency. We hope this would solve the vast illiteracy that causes abject poverty in rural Nigeria.
3. The government should revive the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and reposition the agriculture sector to provide jobs for Nigerian youths. As we stated before in this study, technical schools and polytechnics should be prioritized in educational policy for excellent vocational education/skill development.
4. Federal, state, and local governments in Nigeria need collaborative security arrangements. The central/federal government's complete control over security must be addressed. Community policing comes up here. This security configuration should create a village, community, municipal, state, and federal committee to provide critical security information to security authorities at their locations. This will help identify criminals, sponsors, and hideouts in the country.
5. Finally, the FG should revamp Nigeria's intelligence system and strengthen its security apparatus. This will help reduce hoodlum bombings, robberies, kidnappings, and violent crimes in the country.
6. For all these to be achieved, quality education for the masses is key.

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